

An OPTION for Adjunct Faculty Success: Supporting Adjunct Faculty

Kimberly Luke

The University of Arizona Global Campus

Author Notes

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Kimberly Luke, the designer of the OPTION framework, can be reached at

kimberly.luke@uagc.edu. The OPTION framework was developed by the author for this presentation and is not a UAGC initiative.

Abstract

With nearly half of all faculty (49%) serving in part-time positions in 2023, the needs of adjunct faculty who work part time and have fixed appointments directly impact student success in U.S. colleges and universities (Colby, 2025). The OPTION framework is designed to support the diverse needs of adjunct faculty through every stage of their career from initial onboarding to ongoing professional development. The framework addresses adjuncts' needs through Orientation, Professional development, Teaching resources, Input, Outreach, and Networking. An analysis of each step in the framework can help universities incorporate the framework into their training and support systems for adjunct faculty. An online faculty lounge provides a vital source of information for and contact with adjunct faculty. The results of a user survey conducted in UAGC's Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge in August and September 2025 corroborate the effectiveness of multiple aspects of the OPTION framework.

Keywords: adjunct faculty, faculty lounge, professional development, outreach, networking

An OPTION for Adjunct Faculty Success: Supporting Adjunct Faculty

Adjunct faculty positions provide both benefits and challenges. They are more cost effective, allow institutions to adapt to the changing needs of their student population, and offer flexible schedules without research requirements (Earnshaw & Bodine Al-Sharif, 2025; Knaggs, 2024). Adjuncts who continue to work in their fields bring industry experience (Knaggs, 2024). Unfortunately, adjuncts may not be as integrated into university culture or be aware of the resources available for their success (Earnshaw & Bodine Al-Sharif, 2025; Knaggs, 2024). They may have little or no contact with course designers, lack job security, struggle with low pay and no benefits, have little access to professional development and networking, and feel undervalued within university culture (Earnshaw & Bodine Al-Sharif, 2025).

The diverse needs of adjunct faculty can be addressed through the OPTION framework of Orientation, Professional development, Teaching resources, Input, Outreach, and Networking. An online faculty lounge can facilitate multiple steps within the OPTION framework. A user survey of the Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge at The University of Arizona Global Campus (UAGC) supports the effectiveness of four of the six steps within the OPTION framework.

Framework

The OPTION framework was created by the author to illustrate important steps in supporting adjunct faculty. While it has not been presented to any university for wholesale implementation, examples of its steps are evident at the program and university level at UAGC.

UAGC provides an asynchronous, online format in which adult students take one, five-week course at a time as they pursue their degrees. The faculty includes 1,923 adjuncts and 101 full-time faculty (The University of Arizona Global Campus, n.d.). Full-time faculty design the courses, and adjunct faculty teach them through announcements, discussions, and grading

feedback. UAGC offers a Bachelor of Arts in Liberal Arts degree with an interdisciplinary focus. The program currently has about 160 majors.

The first step of the OPTION framework is Orientation. At UAGC, new faculty members participate in a two-week orientation called the New Faculty Experience (NFE; UAGC Faculty Affairs, 2025). During Week 1, faculty complete asynchronous training modules that highlight UAGC's Culture of Care and teaching requirements (UAGC Faculty Affairs, 2025). They perform human resources tasks that include FERPA and CLERY trainings (UAGC Faculty Affairs, 2025). During Week 2, faculty work in a simulated course to perform instructional tasks (UAGC Faculty Affairs, 2025). A faculty coach monitors and supports new faculty (UAGC Faculty Affairs, 2025). The orientation teaches the requirements of faculty's roles in Week 1 and allows faculty to apply their training in a simulated class with instructional support in Week 2. In the Liberal Arts program, new adjunct instructors are paired with a mentor during their first class. Mentors review new instructors' classes, answer questions, and direct faculty to resources.

The second step of the OPTION framework is Professional development. UAGC requires adjunct faculty to complete one professional development opportunity for every class taught. Faculty can access professional development opportunities through the Faculty Affairs website. The Liberal Arts program also offers targeted professional development through its Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge three times each year. Webinars present updates and practical strategies for meeting teaching expectations. The lounge also houses a library of short, instructive videos created by UAGC's Faculty Support and Development Committee.

The third step of the OPTION framework is Teaching resources. UAGC has established a searchable, 24/7 resource for faculty called FacultyHelp that is accessible within Canvas. FacultyHelp presents answers to nearly 300 faculty questions (UAGC Faculty Affairs, n.d.).

Resources such as training modules and job aids are also available through the Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge. Since UAGC courses are standardized, teaching materials such as announcements, videos, and instructor guidance can be shared in the lounge.

The fourth step of the OPTION framework is Input. All faculty members receive a yearly review of the extent to which they meet the required teaching expectations in their courses. Reviewers assess the quality of faculty's announcements, discussion facilitation, and grading and feedback. Mentoring with full-time faculty members is available for faculty struggling with meeting teaching expectations.

The fifth step of the OPTION framework is Outreach. Faculty Affairs provides a weekly Faculty Digest announcement that highlights news, events, and resources. The Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge shares announcements and emails about changes in university policies and provides classroom announcements in HTML format that faculty can incorporate into their classrooms.

The sixth and final step of the OPTION framework is Networking. The Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge provides information about course leads and includes the names and contact information of faculty who contribute teaching resources. Live webinars also provide networking opportunities.

Methodology

Launched in February 2023, the Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge was designed to provide several steps of the OPTION framework within the program by offering Professional development, Teaching resources, Outreach, and Networking. To determine the lounge's effectiveness, a user survey was designed in Microsoft Forms and was shared with the members of the lounge by a link in emails and announcements within the lounge. Out of 95 adjunct faculty

members, 15 completed the survey during a three-week period from August 12, 2025, to September 2, 2025. The survey included 16 questions and took an average of 6-7 minutes to complete. While this study did not address the effectiveness of the Orientation and Input stages of the OPTION framework since they were not facilitated by the Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge, the value of providing adjunct faculty orientation and periodic instructional review is supported by scholarly literature.

Results

Survey findings revealed that the lounge was serving as a central repository for Professional development. The course resources section houses links to job aids and training. One third of respondents accessed this section monthly, and another third accessed it every six months. The webinars section houses periodic webinars and was visited by one third of respondents monthly and by another third every six months. The Faculty Support and Development Committee's video library teaches new skills and helps faculty refine teaching practices. One third of respondents visited monthly while 27% visited every six months.

While live webinar attendance is low with only 7% attending frequently, more than half of respondents reported watching webinar recordings frequently. The user survey also assessed the effectiveness of the webinars. Not all respondents had attended or viewed the webinars, which led them to select "not applicable" when rating their effectiveness. Of those who did provide a rating, all agreed that the webinars cover the stated learning aims, 92% believed the webinars clarify policies and procedures, and 83% asserted that the time devoted to webinars is well spent. Webinars provided practical strategies for 83% of respondents who provided a rating, and 92% of respondents have incorporated strategies from the webinars into their teaching practices.

The lounge provides a platform to share Teaching resources with full-time faculty contributing resources such as announcements, videos, and instructor guidance for the courses that they design. The teaching tools section supports specific classes and was visited by 40% of respondents monthly and 27% of respondents every six months. The frequency and usefulness of the teaching tools was assessed with 60% of respondents reporting using them occasionally and 33% using them frequently. All respondents agreed that the announcements were helpful with 60% finding them very useful. All respondents who provided a rating reported that videos were helpful. The instructor guidance was rated useful by 93% of respondents who provided a rating.

Offering Outreach about updates and policy changes was another goal that the user survey showed the lounge was performing. The lounge was developed within a Canvas shell like the classrooms in which faculty teach. Members of the lounge can set notifications within Canvas to alert them when new announcements are posted. This allows them to monitor updates within their faculty email without going into the lounge directly. Two thirds of respondents had set notifications to receive these announcements. Faculty also reported accessing the lounge directly with 47% of respondents visiting monthly and 27% visiting weekly. The announcements section is most popular with 47% of respondents visiting weekly and 20% visiting monthly.

The Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge has been successful in sharing announcements about campus news and events that faculty can post in their classrooms. More than half of respondents reported posting these announcements several times each course while 27% posted once per course.

One of the purposes of the lounge was Networking between faculty and offering adjunct faculty relevant contact information. All faculty who rated the webinars asserted that the webinars introduced them to other faculty in their fields, and 89% of respondents agreed that

webinars offered opportunities to converse with colleagues. Adjunct faculty had vital contact information with 93% of respondents answering that they knew who to contact with questions in the classroom. The course leads section, which provides biographies and contact information, attracted 40% of respondents monthly.

Conclusions and Implications

The OPTION framework is a comprehensive approach to meet the needs of adjunct faculty. An online faculty lounge can serve as a vital hub to implement this framework. According to a user survey of the Liberal Arts Faculty Lounge at UAGC, adjunct faculty found value in this framework by accessing Professional development and Teaching resources, receiving administration Outreach about updates and policy changes, and using the lounge as a forum for Networking.

An online faculty lounge can be created easily in a university's learning management system and updated through weekly monitoring. A lounge serves as a significant source of connection that helps adjunct faculty improve their practice, align their policies with university priorities, and receive the university support that their essential role in the education of the student population deserves.

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